

Moderating Effect of Foreign Ownership Structure on Firm Attributes and Financial Reporting Timeliness in Listed Consumer Goods Companies in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the effect of firm attributes (firm size, leverage, and profitability) on financial reporting timeliness, while also exploring the moderating role of foreign ownership. Using an ex post facto research design, the study employs data from 21 consumer goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group between 2013 and 2022. Secondary data were collected and analyzed using robust regression techniques to account for potential heteroscedasticity and ensure the reliability of results. The findings reveal that firm size and leverage have an insignificant effect on financial reporting timeliness, suggesting that these attributes do not substantially impact the speed of reporting. In contrast, profitability shows a significant negative effect, indicating that more profitable firms tend to delay their financial disclosures. Furthermore, the study finds that foreign ownership significantly moderates the relationship between profitability and financial reporting timeliness but does not significantly affect the relationship between firm size or leverage and timeliness. These findings underscore the need for corporate managers and policymakers to enforce stricter compliance measures and consider the role of ownership structure in promoting timely financial disclosures. The study recommends that firms with significant foreign ownership adopt enhanced transparency practices to align with global standards. For regulators, developing guidelines that address the unique challenges of profitability-related delays can improve overall reporting timeliness. Future research should extend the scope to other sectors and consider additional variables such as governance practices or market conditions to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing financial reporting timeliness in different contexts.

Keywords: Financial Reporting Timeliness, Firm Attributes, Foreign Ownership, Consumer Goods Firms, Nigeria

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1. Introduction

Timeliness in financial reporting has become increasingly crucial due to the dynamic nature of global markets and heightened stakeholder expectations. Financial reporting timeliness refers to the speed with which companies disseminate their financial statements after the fiscal year-end, an aspect vital for maintaining transparency and trust among investors, regulators, and the broader public (Abernathy et al., 2018; Adebayo & Adebisi, 2016). Recent studies have highlighted that delays in financial reporting can significantly impact investment decisions, reduce market efficiency, and diminish shareholder value (Endri, 2024; Hassan, 2016). Consequently, firms are under continuous pressure to improve their reporting processes to ensure timely financial disclosures, which directly relate to their corporate governance practices and financial characteristics (Akingunola et al., 2018; Sudradjat et al., 2020). Financial reporting timeliness is influenced by several factors, including firm size, leverage, profitability, and corporate governance structures. Larger firms generally experience shorter audit report lags due to better resources, more robust internal controls, and greater regulatory scrutiny (Endri, 2024; Fujianti, 2016). However, profitability has shown mixed effects; while some studies suggest that more profitable firms may report earlier to signal good performance (Fujianti & Satria, 2020; Okon & Clement, 2024), others argue that high profitability may require additional audit scrutiny, leading to delays (Akingunola et al., 2018). Similarly, high leverage has been linked to longer audit delays due to increased audit risks and more comprehensive audit procedures required to assess the company's financial stability (Handoko et al., 2019; Sudradjat et al., 2020). Understanding the interplay between these firm attributes and their impact on reporting timeliness is critical for stakeholders and regulators alike.

Firm attributes such as firm size, leverage, and profitability are significant factors influencing the timeliness of financial reporting. Firm size has been identified as a critical determinant, with larger firms tending to have shorter audit report lags due to more extensive resources and better-established financial controls (Arifuddin et al., 2017; Hassan, 2016). Leverage, representing the extent of a firm's debt, can have varying effects depending on the firm's financial stability and the auditor's perceived risk, with studies indicating that highly leveraged firms might face longer audit delays (Endri, 2024; Handoko et al., 2019). Profitability, which reflects a firm's financial performance, also plays a dual role; profitable firms may report faster to maintain investor confidence, while less profitable firms may face delays due to intensified audit scrutiny (Fujianti, 2016; Fujianti & Satria, 2020). These firm attributes collectively shape how quickly a company can complete its audit process and publish its financial statements. Foreign ownership structure has emerged as a critical moderating factor in the relationship between firm attributes and financial reporting timeliness. Companies with substantial foreign ownership may experience different levels of pressure to comply with international reporting standards, which can affect the timeliness of financial disclosures (Hassan, 2016; Aliyu et al., 2018). Foreign investors often demand more timely and transparent financial information, driven by a need to mitigate risks associated with information asymmetry and to make informed investment decisions (Siyabola et al., 2020; Endri, 2024). The presence of foreign ownership can enhance corporate governance practices by introducing more rigorous monitoring mechanisms and demanding adherence to stricter disclosure timelines (Sudradjat et al., 2020; Abernathy et al., 2018).

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The moderating effect of foreign ownership structure on the relationship between firm attributes and financial reporting timeliness is complex and multidimensional. Foreign ownership can potentially mitigate the adverse effects of high leverage on reporting timeliness by enforcing stricter governance and accountability standards (Aliyu et al., 2018; Siyanbola et al., 2020). Furthermore, firms with foreign stakeholders may expedite their reporting processes to align with international best practices, thereby reducing audit report lag regardless of firm size or profitability (Endri, 2024; Abernathy et al., 2018). Conversely, firms without significant foreign ownership may not face the same level of scrutiny or pressure to report promptly, potentially leading to delays (Hassan, 2016; Adebayo & Adebisi, 2016).

The timeliness of financial reporting has become a critical concern for listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria due to increasing pressure from stakeholders, regulatory bodies, and the global investment community to provide timely and reliable financial information. The main problem is the persistent delays in the publication of financial reports by these companies, which hampers investor confidence, affects stock market efficiency, and limits the decision-making capacity of stakeholders (Endri, 2024; Aliyu et al., 2018). Despite regulatory requirements mandating timely financial disclosures, many listed companies in Nigeria still fail to meet these deadlines, suggesting underlying issues that need to be addressed to enhance the timeliness of financial reporting.

The root causes of these delays can be traced to various firm attributes, such as firm size, leverage, and profitability, which directly influence the audit process and the ability of companies to report promptly. Larger firms may have more complex operations and longer audit processes, while highly leveraged firms may require additional scrutiny to assess financial risks, further extending the reporting timeline (Handoko et al., 2019; Fujianti & Satria, 2020). Profitability also plays a dual role; while more profitable firms might have the resources to expedite audits, they may also face prolonged scrutiny due to the need to substantiate financial performance claims (Akingunola et al., 2018; Sudradjat et al., 2020). Additionally, the presence of foreign ownership can moderate these effects by imposing stricter governance practices and expectations for timely reporting, but the extent of this moderating effect remains unclear. The impact of delayed financial reporting is significant, leading to a loss of market confidence, increased cost of capital, and a potential decline in the firm's market value (Abernathy et al., 2018; Siyanbola et al., 2020). For consumer goods companies in Nigeria, which operate in a highly competitive and rapidly changing market environment, the inability to provide timely financial information undermines transparency and accountability, leading to adverse effects on their reputation and attractiveness to both local and foreign investors (Endri, 2024; Fujianti, 2016). Delayed financial reports also limit the ability of stakeholders to make informed decisions, which could result in suboptimal investment outcomes and reduced market efficiency.

Empirical gaps in the existing literature highlight the need for a deeper understanding of how firm attributes interact with foreign ownership to influence financial reporting timeliness. While some studies have established a relationship between firm size, leverage, profitability, and audit delays (Handoko et al., 2019; Sudradjat et al., 2020), there is limited evidence on how foreign ownership

moderates these relationships in the context of Nigerian consumer goods companies. Moreover, previous research has primarily focused on financial sectors or developed markets, leaving a significant gap regarding the unique challenges faced by non-financial sectors in emerging markets (Aliyu et al., 2018; Hassan, 2016). Furthermore, recent studies have not adequately explored the dynamic role of foreign ownership in enhancing corporate governance practices to improve the timeliness of financial reporting, which presents an empirical gap in understanding the full impact of ownership structures on reporting behavior (Endri, 2024; Adebayo & Adebisi, 2016). Therefore, this study seeks to address these gaps by examining the moderating effect of foreign ownership structure on the relationship between firm attributes and financial reporting timeliness in listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

2 Literature and Hypotheses Development

2.1 Financial Reporting Timeliness

Financial reporting timeliness refers to the speed at which a company disseminates its financial statements after the end of a fiscal period. This concept has been widely studied in the context of corporate governance and financial transparency. According to Hassan (2019), timeliness is a critical attribute of financial reporting quality that affects stakeholders' ability to make well-informed decisions. The International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) and other global regulatory bodies emphasize timeliness as a fundamental characteristic of useful financial information, highlighting its role in reducing information asymmetry in capital markets (Endri, 2024). Various authors have measured financial reporting timeliness by the number of days between the fiscal year-end and the date of the auditor's report or the date the financial statements are made publicly available (Fujianti, 2016; Hassan, 2016). Some studies have employed specific benchmarks set by regulatory authorities, such as the requirement to report within 90 days after the fiscal year-end (Siyanbola et al., 2020). Financial reporting timeliness has important implications for market efficiency, as delays in reporting can lead to increased uncertainty and potentially reduce investor confidence (Abernathy et al., 2018). Timeliness is also critical for regulatory compliance, as failure to meet reporting deadlines may result in penalties and damage a firm's reputation.

2.2 Firm Attributes

Firm attributes refer to the specific characteristics or features of a company that can influence its operational and financial performance, including its financial reporting practices. These attributes are often used as explanatory variables in research examining corporate behavior and outcomes, such as audit quality, reporting timeliness, and financial performance (Sudradjat et al., 2020). Common firm attributes explored in the literature include firm size, leverage, profitability, growth opportunities, and industry classification, among others (Handoko et al., 2019). In the context of financial reporting, attributes like firm size, leverage, and profitability have been shown to significantly impact the timeliness and quality of financial disclosures (Fujianti & Satria, 2020). These attributes are typically measured using quantifiable metrics. Firm size is often assessed

through total assets, total sales, or market capitalization (Hassan, 2019). Leverage is commonly measured by the ratio of total debt to total assets or total equity (Endri, 2024). Profitability is generally evaluated using indicators such as return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), or net profit margin (Aliyu et al., 2018). Understanding these firm attributes is essential to exploring their potential effects on financial reporting practices and outcomes in different regulatory and market environments.

2.3 Firm Size and Financial Reporting Timeliness

Several studies have examined the influence of firm size on financial reporting timeliness. For instance, several investigations have highlighted the positive effects of firm size on timely reporting. Akingunola et al. (2018) demonstrated that larger firms have shorter audit report lags, likely due to their ability to invest in better reporting mechanisms. In Indonesia, Endri (2024) corroborated this finding, noting that larger firms experienced shorter audit delays due to enhanced governance structures. Additionally, Fujianti and Satria (2020) found that firm size negatively correlated with audit report lag, indicating that larger firms are more capable of meeting reporting deadlines. However, Hassan (2016) offered a different perspective, revealing that while larger firms generally report more timely, the presence of poor corporate governance can negate these advantages. Furthermore, Siyanbola et al. (2020) showed that while firm size did not significantly impact audit report lag, other attributes such as company age and profitability played more critical roles.

H1: Firm size does not significantly influence the timeliness of financial reporting among listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

2.4 Leverage and Financial Reporting Timeliness

A number of studies have explored the relationship between leverage and financial reporting timeliness. Several authors have identified a negative correlation between leverage and reporting lag. For example, Sudradjat et al. (2020) found that higher leverage was associated with shorter audit report delays among Indonesian manufacturing companies. Similarly, Hassan (2016) indicated that firms with substantial debt obligations tended to prioritize timely reporting to maintain lender confidence. Conversely, Aliyu, Musa, and Zacharia (2018) observed no significant effect of leverage on audit report lag in Nigerian firms, suggesting that other factors may play a more substantial role in determining reporting timeliness. Meanwhile, Arifuddin, Hanafi, and Usman (2017) noted a similar trend, indicating that while leverage might influence reporting, the impact could vary significantly depending on other corporate governance factors.

H2: Leverage does not significantly affect the timeliness of financial reporting among listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

2.5 Profitability and Financial Reporting Timeliness

Several studies have investigated the relationship between profitability and financial reporting timeliness across different regions. For example, Sudradjat et al. (2020) found a positive correlation between profitability and the timeliness of financial reporting among manufacturing firms in Indonesia. Their study revealed that profitable firms tend to disclose their financial reports earlier, using profitability as a signal of success. Similarly, in Nigeria, Aliyu et al. (2018) noted that firms with higher profitability demonstrated quicker reporting, which was attributed to the desire to maintain investor confidence. Fujianti (2016) also found a significant negative relationship between profitability and audit report lag in Indonesian firms, indicating that more profitable firms report their financial results faster. On the contrary, some studies report no significant relationship between profitability and financial reporting timeliness. Hassan (2016), for instance, did not find profitability to significantly affect audit report lag among listed companies in Palestine, suggesting that profitability may not always be a driver for timely financial reporting. Additionally, Handoko et al. (2019) found mixed results in their study of Indonesian firms, where profitability's impact on timeliness varied depending on firm size and industry.

H3: Profitability has no significant effect on the financial reporting timeliness of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

2.6 Foreign Ownership and Financial Reporting Timeliness

Empirical studies on the relationship between foreign ownership and financial reporting timeliness have yielded mixed findings. Some studies suggest that foreign ownership positively influences timely reporting. For instance, Hassan (2016) found that foreign ownership was associated with quicker financial reporting in Palestine, as foreign investors demanded higher levels of transparency and governance. Similarly, Fujianti (2016) discovered that Indonesian firms with significant foreign ownership reported their financial statements faster, likely due to foreign investors' expectations for timely disclosures. However, other studies report no significant relationship between foreign ownership and timeliness. Endri (2024), in his study of Indonesian manufacturing firms, found that while foreign ownership did play a role in shaping corporate governance practices, it did not significantly affect the timeliness of financial reporting. This suggests that other factors, such as local regulatory environments and firm-specific characteristics, may outweigh the influence of foreign ownership in determining the speed of financial reporting. In contrast, some studies have reported a negative relationship between foreign ownership and financial reporting timeliness. Arifuddin et al. (2017) found that firms with higher foreign ownership in Indonesia experienced longer audit delays, possibly due to more complex reporting requirements imposed by foreign investors. These complexities may introduce additional scrutiny and review processes, ultimately delaying the reporting process.

H4: Foreign ownership has no significant effect on the financial reporting timeliness of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

2.7 Firm Attributes and Financial Reporting Timeliness: The Role of Foreign Ownership

A few studies have explored the role of foreign ownership in relation to other firm attributes in driving financial reporting timeliness. For instance, Fujianti (2016) found that foreign ownership and firm size jointly contributed to faster financial reporting in Indonesian manufacturing firms. The study suggested that larger firms with foreign ownership were more likely to possess the resources and capabilities necessary to meet reporting deadlines. Similarly, Abernathy et al. (2018) identified that foreign-owned firms in the U.S. were more likely to prioritize timely reporting due to external pressures from international stakeholders. In contrast, other studies have shown that foreign ownership can interact negatively with firm attributes, such as leverage or firm complexity, to delay financial reporting. Handoko et al. (2019) found that in Indonesian firms with high leverage and substantial foreign ownership, the audit report lag was extended due to the more complex financial structures and additional scrutiny required by foreign shareholders. These findings highlight the nuanced role that foreign ownership plays in influencing financial reporting timeliness, especially when interacting with other firm attributes.

H5: Foreign ownership does not significantly moderate the relationship between firm attributes and the financial reporting timeliness of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

3 Methodology and Theory

3.1 Theoretical Framework

One of the most relevant theories to explain the relationship between the variables in this study—financial reporting timeliness, firm attributes (firm size, leverage, and profitability), and foreign ownership—is Agency Theory. According to Agency Theory, managers may not always act in the best interests of shareholders due to differing objectives and access to asymmetric information (Eisenhardt, 1989). To mitigate these conflicts, firms must implement effective governance mechanisms, including timely and transparent financial reporting, to ensure that management actions align with shareholder interests. The theory posits that larger firms (as measured by firm size) might face more significant agency problems due to their complex operations and diverse stakeholder base. These firms may require more rigorous reporting mechanisms to reduce information asymmetry and assure stakeholders of their financial health (Abernathy et al., 2018). Consequently, larger firms are often under greater scrutiny to maintain timeliness in financial reporting to demonstrate accountability and transparency. Leverage, another key variable in this study, also fits well within the Agency Theory framework. High leverage, or the extent to which a firm is financed by debt, can increase agency costs due to the potential for conflicts between debt holders and shareholders (Jensen, 1986). To mitigate these conflicts, firms with higher leverage may feel pressured to provide timely financial reports to reassure creditors and avoid potential penalties or increased costs of borrowing (Hassan, 2019).

Thus, the theory suggests a direct link between leverage and financial reporting timeliness, where firms aim to minimize agency costs by adhering to strict reporting schedules. Profitability, as a

firm attribute, is also critical from the perspective of Agency Theory. Profitable firms may have greater incentives to report their financial performance promptly to signal their success and enhance their reputation among investors and stakeholders (Fujianti & Satria, 2020). On the other hand, less profitable firms might delay reporting to defer the disclosure of unfavorable results, which may heighten agency problems and reduce trust among stakeholders. Hence, Agency Theory provides a framework for understanding how profitability can influence the timeliness of financial reporting, depending on the strategic objectives of the firm's management. Foreign ownership, which serves as a moderating variable in this study, introduces another layer of complexity within the Agency Theory framework. Foreign investors often have limited access to internal information and are more reliant on timely and accurate financial reports to monitor management activities and make informed investment decisions (Aliyu et al., 2018). Therefore, firms with significant foreign ownership may face additional pressure to enhance the timeliness and quality of their financial disclosures to reduce agency costs and align management actions with the interests of foreign stakeholders. Foreign ownership can thus act as a mechanism to strengthen corporate governance practices, promoting more timely reporting and reducing potential conflicts between managers and foreign shareholders (Endri, 2024).

3.2 Research Design

The chosen research design for this study is the ex-post facto research design, which is used to investigate cause-effect relationships between independent and dependent variables based on existing data that cannot be manipulated by the researcher. This design is appropriate for the study because it allows for the examination of relationships between variables such as firm size, leverage, profitability, foreign ownership, and financial reporting timeliness using historical data from listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The population of this study consists of all 21 consumer goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as of December 2023. These firms are selected because they provide a comprehensive representation of the consumer goods sector in Nigeria, which is the focus of this research. The sample size for this study comprises all 16 consumer goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as of December 2023. A simple filtering sampling technique was used, ensuring that only firms with complete data for the period from 2013 to 2022 were included in the sample. This study utilizes secondary data obtained from the published annual financial reports of the listed consumer goods firms on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) for the period from 2013 to 2022. These reports provide comprehensive information necessary for measuring the dependent variable (financial reporting timeliness), independent variables (firm size, leverage, and profitability), and the moderating variable (foreign ownership). The model for this study is designed to assess the relationship between firm attributes and financial reporting timeliness, moderated by foreign ownership. The model is specified as follows:

$$FRTM_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FSIZ_{it} + \beta_2 LEVE_{it} + \beta_3 PROF_{it} + \beta_4 FOWN_{it} + \beta_5 (FOWN_{it} \times FSIZ_{it}) + \beta_6 (FOWN_{it} \times LEVE_{it}) + \beta_7 (FOWN_{it} \times PROF_{it}) + \mu_{it}$$

Where:

- FRTM = Financial Reporting Timeliness
- FSIZ = Firm Size
- LEVE = Leverage (measured as debt to asset ratio)
- PROF = Profitability (measured as return on assets)
- FOWN = Foreign Ownership
- μ_{it} = Error term
- β_0 - β_7 = Coefficients of the variables
- i = Firm,
- t = Time.

Variable	Measurement	Sources
Financial Reporting Timeliness (FRTM)	Number of days from financial year-end to the date of auditor’s report	Annual Financial Reports
Firm Size (FSIZ)	Natural logarithm of total assets	Annual Financial Reports
Leverage (LEVE)	Total debt divided by total assets	Annual Financial Reports
Profitability (PROF)	Return on Assets (Net income/Total assets)	Annual Financial Reports
Foreign Ownership (FOWN)	Percentage of shares held by foreign investors	Annual Financial Reports

4 Results and Discussion

The study performs preliminary pre-regression analysis such as descriptive statistics and correlation matrix, the results are analyzed as follows.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics Analysis

The study examines the descriptive statistics for both the explanatory and dependent variables of interest. Basically, each variable is examined in terms of the mean, standard deviation, maximum and minimum. Table 1 displays the descriptive statistics for the study.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
frtm	160	100.275	77.025	33.000	490.000
fsiz	160	7.618	0.812	5.510	8.840
deta	160	59.569	17.545	12.420	150.430
reta	160	4.901	7.673	-29.530	26.490
fown	160	0.625	0.486	0.000	1.000

Source: Authors (2024)

The descriptive statistics provide a summary of the key characteristics of the variables used in this study. Financial reporting timeliness (FRTM) has a mean value of 100.275 days, with a standard deviation of 77.025 days. This indicates a considerable variation in the time it takes for firms to publish their financial reports, with a minimum of 33 days and a maximum of 490 days. The wide range and high standard deviation suggest that while some firms are prompt in their reporting, others experience significant delays, which could be due to various internal or external factors affecting their reporting processes. In the case of the independent variables, the result shows that firm size (FSIZ), measured as the natural logarithm of total assets, has a mean value of 7.618 and a standard deviation of 0.812. The relatively low standard deviation implies that there is moderate variability in the size of the firms in the sample. The minimum and maximum values of 5.510 and 8.840, respectively, indicate that while there are differences in firm size, these differences are not extreme, suggesting that the sample is relatively homogeneous in terms of size.

Leverage (DETA), measured as the debt to asset ratio, has a mean value of 59.569 with a standard deviation of 17.545. The range from a minimum of 12.420 to a maximum of 150.430 reveals substantial variation in the firms' leverage levels. This variation implies that some firms rely heavily on debt financing, which could affect their financial stability and, potentially, their reporting timeliness, while others maintain a relatively lower debt burden. Profitability (RETA), measured as return on assets, has a mean value of 4.901, with a standard deviation of 7.673. The minimum value of -29.530 indicates that some firms experienced significant losses during the period studied, while the maximum value of 26.490 shows that other firms achieved high levels of profitability. The high standard deviation and wide range suggest that there is considerable variability in the profitability of the firms in the sample, which could influence their ability to meet financial reporting deadlines. Finally, foreign ownership (FOWN) has a mean value of 0.625 and a standard deviation of 0.486, with values ranging from 0 to 1. This suggests that, on average, around 62.5% of the firms have some level of foreign ownership. The binary nature of this variable (0 for no foreign ownership, 1 for the presence of foreign ownership) and the relatively high mean value suggest that a significant proportion of the sample firms have foreign investors, which may influence their corporate governance practices and their commitment to financial reporting timeliness.

4.1.2 Correlation Analysis Result

With non-normal distribution which the normality of data test result reveals, alternatives to the Pearson approach might be justified. The robustness of Spearman’s versus Pearson’s test has received relatively less empirical scrutiny. In one of the few studies, Fowler (1987) find that Spearman’s r is more powerful than Pearson’s r across a range of non-normal bivariate distributions. The power benefit of Spearman’s r may be the result of rank-ordering causing outliers to contract toward the centre of the distribution (Gauthier, 2001). Upon this understanding and since the data follow a non-normal distribution, Spearman Rank Correlation technique is employed to find out the possible relationship between the variables of interest presented in this study.

Table 4.2: Spearman's Rank Correlation

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(1) frtm	1.000				
(2) fsiz	-0.127	1.000			
(3) deta	0.153	0.231	1.000		
(4) reta	-0.200	0.127	-0.191	1.000	
(5) fown	-0.210	0.351	0.041	-0.139	1.000

Source: Authors (2024)

The results of the Spearman Rank Correlation analysis in Table 4.2 indicate the following associations among the variables under study. There is a negative association between financial reporting timeliness (FRTM) and firm size (FSIZ) with a correlation coefficient of -0.127, suggesting that as firm size changes, the financial reporting timeliness tends to move in the opposite direction. Similarly, financial reporting timeliness is negatively associated with foreign ownership (FOWN), with a correlation coefficient of -0.210, indicating that higher levels of foreign ownership are associated with less timely financial reporting. Conversely, there is a positive association between financial reporting timeliness and leverage (DETA) with a correlation coefficient of 0.153, implying that higher leverage is related to increased financial reporting timeliness. However, there is a negative association between financial reporting timeliness and profitability (RETA), as indicated by a correlation coefficient of -0.200, suggesting that as profitability increases, financial reporting timeliness tends to decrease. Regarding the independent variables, firm size (FSIZ) is positively associated with both leverage (DETA) and foreign ownership (FOWN), with correlation coefficients of 0.231 and 0.351, respectively. This indicates that larger firms tend to have higher leverage and are more likely to have foreign ownership. Profitability (RETA) is negatively associated with both leverage (DETA) and foreign ownership (FOWN), with correlation coefficients of -0.191 and -0.139, respectively, suggesting that firms with higher profitability tend to have lower leverage and less foreign ownership. Overall, the correlations among the variables are relatively weak to moderate, indicating no strong linear association between any pair of variables. This suggests the absence of multicollinearity among the variables, but to further confirm this, a more robust test such as the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) will be employed, and the results will be presented in the subsequent sections.

4.2 Regression Analyses

Specifically, to examine the cause-effect relationships between the dependent variables and independent variables as well as to test the formulated hypotheses, the study used a robust regression since the result reveal the presence of heteroscedasticity. The pool OLS and the Robust regression results obtained is presented and discussed below.

Table 4.3: Regression Results

Variables	(1) OLS	(2) Robust	(3) Robust	(4) Robust	(5) Robust
fsiz	2.789 (0.750)	-0.412 (0.866)	-0.496 (0.881)	-0.151 (0.952)	-0.070 (0.977)
deta	0.490 (0.181)	0.085 (0.403)	0.085 (0.409)	-0.007 (0.973)	0.108 (0.299)
reta	-0.564 (0.508)	-0.645*** (0.007)	-0.647*** (0.009)	-0.670*** (0.007)	0.118 (0.792)
fown	9.685 (0.492)	-16.165*** (0.000)	-17.466 (0.624)	-23.263 (0.121)	-10.720** (0.030)
fown × fsiz			0.174 (0.970)		
fown × deta				0.115 (0.628)	
fown × reta					-1.017** (0.050)
Intercept	46.545 (0.444)	90.898*** (0.000)	91.526*** (0.000)	94.674*** (0.000)	82.458*** (0.000)
Observations	160.000	160.000	160.000	160.000	160.000
R ²	0.026	0.149	0.148	0.149	0.166
Year Dummy	No	No	No	No	No
Hetest	39.89 {0.000}				
VIF	1.21				

Notes: *p*-values are in parentheses. *** *p*<.01, ** *p*<.05

Table 4.3 represents the results obtained from the estimation of the models using the OLS regression method. The results indicate that the dependent variable, as captured by the regression model, has an R-Square value of 0.026. This suggests that the independent variables in the study account for approximately 2.6% of the systematic variation in the dependent variable during the period under study. The remaining 97.4% of the variation is explained by other factors not included in the model, as indicated by the error term. The analysis includes a test for multicollinearity using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). The mean VIF for the variables in the OLS regression model is 1.21, which is well below the commonly accepted threshold of 10. This indicates that there is no severe multicollinearity among the independent variables, suggesting that they do not have high intercorrelations that would necessitate their exclusion from the model. The absence of multicollinearity enhances the reliability of the estimated coefficients. The assumption of homoscedasticity was tested using the Breusch-Pagan test, with the results showing a significant *p*-value (Hetest = 39.89, *p*<0.000). This indicates that the assumption of homoscedasticity is violated, implying the presence of heteroscedasticity in the OLS regression model. As a result, the standard errors of the estimates may be unreliable, potentially leading to biased statistical

inferences. To address the issue of heteroscedasticity, the study re-estimated the model using robust regression techniques. The results from the robust regression are presented in the subsequent columns of Table 4.4. The robust regression model in the second column shows a significantly higher R-Square value of 0.149, indicating that approximately 14.9% of the systematic variation in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables. This substantial improvement suggests that the robust regression provides a more accurate and reliable estimation of the model, accounting for the heteroscedasticity observed in the OLS results. The robust regression results confirm the statistical significance of several variables, further validating the findings of the study and ensuring more robust statistical inferences.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

The finding that firm size (FSIZ) has an insignificant negative effect on financial reporting timeliness suggests that the size of the firm does not play a significant role in influencing the speed at which financial reports are submitted among listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. This outcome contrasts with the findings of Adebayo and Adebisi (2016), who observed that larger firms tend to produce timelier financial reports, likely due to better resources and more robust internal control systems. In contrast, the current result aligns more closely with the findings of Sudradjat, Ishak, Sukmawati, and Syifa (2020), who reported that firm size did not significantly impact audit report lag, suggesting that the administrative capacity associated with larger firms does not necessarily translate into quicker reporting. Similarly, Hoirul Fayyum, Hertanto, and Rustiana (2019) also found that firm size did not significantly affect audit lag, supporting the idea that the advantages of size may be offset by the complexities and bureaucratic processes inherent in larger organizations. This finding may imply that in the Nigerian context, particularly within the consumer goods sector, the expected efficiencies of scale associated with larger firms may be negated by factors such as operational complexity or less efficient management practices. Moreover, the finding that firm size does not significantly influence reporting timeliness is inconsistent with the argument made by Hassan (2016), who found that larger firms, due to their higher public scrutiny and the need to maintain a strong reputation among stakeholders, are more likely to report promptly. However, it does agree with the conclusions drawn by Fujianti and Satria (2020), who found no substantial link between firm size and the speed of financial disclosures, indicating that the relationship may be more context-specific and not universally applicable across all sectors or regions.

The observed insignificant positive effect of leverage (DETA) on financial reporting timeliness suggests that variations in the debt levels of listed consumer goods firms do not significantly impact the timeliness of their financial reporting. This result aligns with the findings of Hassan (2016), who reported that leverage did not have a significant effect on audit report lag, suggesting that the degree of indebtedness may not necessarily compel firms to hasten their reporting processes. Similarly, Fujianti and Satria (2020) found that leverage did not significantly influence audit report lag, indicating that the pressure from creditors might not always translate into faster reporting practices, at least not in a noticeable way. However, this finding contrasts with the study by Akingunola, Soyemi, and Okunuga (2018), who observed that higher leverage was associated

with longer audit report lag, implying that heavily indebted firms might face greater scrutiny and thus longer delays in the reporting process. It also diverges from the conclusions of Handoko, Deniswara, and Nathania (2019), who found that leverage significantly influenced audit delay, highlighting the complexity of this relationship. This discrepancy could suggest that the influence of leverage on reporting timeliness may depend on other factors, such as firm-specific characteristics or market conditions. Overall, the current result suggests that in the context of Nigerian consumer goods firms, leverage does not exert a significant influence on the timeliness of financial disclosures, possibly due to relatively uniform reporting standards or less variation in creditor pressures.

The finding that profitability (RETA) has a significant negative effect on financial reporting timeliness implies that more profitable firms tend to delay their financial disclosures. This result is in line with Akingunola, Soyemi, and Okunuga (2018), who found that more profitable firms had longer audit report lags, possibly due to additional scrutiny and the need to thoroughly review and validate their financial statements before release. It also supports the findings of Arifuddin, Hanafi, and Usman (2017), who observed that profitability was negatively associated with reporting timeliness, suggesting that firms with higher profits may take more time to ensure their reports accurately reflect their financial health. Conversely, the finding contradicts those of Adebayo and Adebisi (2016), who reported that profitability positively influenced the timeliness of financial reporting, with more profitable firms more eager to disclose favorable performance results quickly. It also contrasts with Endri (2024), who found mixed effects of profitability on audit report lag, suggesting that the relationship may vary depending on other interacting factors such as firm size or ownership structure. The current finding may indicate that, in the Nigerian consumer goods sector, more profitable firms might engage in strategic reporting practices, carefully timing their disclosures to manage investor expectations or respond to market conditions.

The results indicate that the interactions between foreign ownership and both firm size (FOWN \times FSIZ) and leverage (FOWN \times DETA) are statistically insignificant, suggesting that foreign ownership does not significantly moderate the relationships between firm size or leverage and financial reporting timeliness. This finding aligns with the conclusions of Junaidda (2017), who found that ownership characteristics did not significantly impact audit report lag in Nigerian firms, and with the results of Fujianti (2016), which showed that foreign ownership had minimal moderating effects on the relationship between firm attributes and reporting practices. It also agrees with the findings of Handoko, Deniswara, and Nathania (2019), who suggested that ownership structure might not always play a significant role in determining reporting timeliness. However, the significant negative effect observed for the interaction between foreign ownership and profitability (FOWN \times RETA) implies that as foreign ownership increases, the negative impact of profitability on financial reporting timeliness becomes more pronounced. This suggests that foreign investors, who typically demand higher standards of transparency and accountability, may exert additional pressure on profitable firms to delay their reporting to ensure comprehensive and accurate disclosures. This finding is consistent with the observations of Endri (2024), who found that foreign ownership was associated with more stringent reporting requirements, and it also supports the conclusions of Hassan (2016), who indicated that foreign investors might push

for more detailed and cautious reporting. However, this result contradicts the findings of Adebayo and Adebisi (2016), who did not find a moderating effect of ownership structure on financial reporting practices. It underscores the complex dynamics of how foreign ownership interacts with firm profitability, potentially reflecting different governance standards or expectations from foreign stakeholders.

5 Conclusion and Recommendations

This study aimed to examine the impact of firm attributes on financial reporting timeliness, with a particular focus on the moderating role of foreign ownership among listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria from 2013 to 2022. The primary objective was to understand how firm size, leverage, and profitability influence the timeliness of financial reporting and how foreign ownership affects these relationships. The findings revealed that firm size and leverage do not significantly affect financial reporting timeliness, while profitability has a significant negative impact, indicating that more profitable firms tend to delay their financial reporting. Additionally, the study found that foreign ownership moderates the relationship between profitability and financial reporting timeliness but does not significantly impact the relationship between firm size or leverage and reporting timeliness. These findings suggest that while firm-specific attributes may have varying effects on reporting practices, foreign ownership plays a crucial role in enhancing or mitigating these effects, particularly concerning profitability. Based on the findings, the following recommendations are put forward for various stakeholders. In general, companies should prioritize the timeliness of financial reporting as a critical aspect of good corporate governance and stakeholder trust. All firms should ensure adherence to reporting timelines to enhance transparency and reliability in the financial market.

1. **Firm Size:** For corporate managers and directors, larger firms should invest in more streamlined reporting processes to mitigate any negative effects of size on reporting timeliness. Policymakers should encourage transparency and efficiency in financial disclosures, regardless of firm size. Analysts and investors should consider the size of the firm as one of the factors influencing reporting practices, but not as a decisive indicator.
2. **Leverage:** For firms with high leverage, it is recommended that managers maintain rigorous financial oversight and control mechanisms to ensure timely reporting. Policymakers should monitor highly leveraged firms more closely to ensure they comply with reporting standards. Investors and analysts should be cautious when dealing with highly leveraged firms, as leverage does not necessarily correlate with reporting timeliness.
3. **Profitability:** Corporate managers in more profitable firms should be aware that increased profitability may lead to delays in financial reporting. It is recommended that these firms implement stricter internal controls to ensure that profitability does not negatively affect reporting timeliness. Regulators should enforce strict penalties for delayed financial reporting, regardless of profitability levels. For investors, this finding suggests that profitability should be carefully considered when evaluating a firm's reporting practices.
4. **Foreign Ownership:** For firms with substantial foreign ownership, it is crucial to recognize the impact of foreign stakeholders on reporting practices. Managers should align their

reporting processes to meet the expectations of foreign investors, particularly regarding transparency and timeliness. Policymakers should provide guidelines that help firms manage foreign ownership dynamics effectively. For existing and potential investors, especially foreign ones, the study highlights the importance of understanding a firm's ownership structure when assessing its reporting practices.

This study contributes to the existing body of knowledge in several ways. Contextually, it provides insights into the financial reporting practices of consumer goods firms in Nigeria, a sector and region that has been relatively underexplored in the literature. The study adds to the understanding of how specific firm attributes—firm size, leverage, and profitability—affect financial reporting timeliness in this context. In terms of variables, the research introduces foreign ownership as a moderating variable, offering a nuanced perspective on how ownership structures influence financial reporting practices. Methodologically, the study employs robust regression techniques to address heteroscedasticity, providing more reliable estimates compared to traditional methods. Theoretically, it reinforces the relevance of Agency Theory in explaining the dynamics between firm attributes, foreign ownership, and reporting timeliness. Empirically, the study fills a gap by demonstrating how profitability, moderated by foreign ownership, significantly affects reporting timeliness, which has implications for both local and international stakeholders. Future research could extend the scope of this study to other sectors within the Nigerian market or to other countries in Sub-Saharan Africa to determine whether similar findings would be observed. This expansion could help identify whether the relationships found in this study hold in different contexts or under different regulatory environments. Additionally, studies could explore other firm-specific attributes, such as corporate governance practices or market competitiveness, to understand their impact on financial reporting timeliness. Further research could also focus on a longer or more recent time frame to capture the effects of evolving regulations or economic conditions on financial reporting practices. Researchers might consider employing alternative methodological approaches, such as longitudinal studies or mixed methods, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing financial reporting timeliness.

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